

KEY INDICATORS

With 562,395 hectares, Czechia ranked second among the EU-13 countries of the European Union in 2022 (after Romania). Also in terms of organic area share, it was the number two EU-13 country (16.0% of total farmland), following Estonia. Growth from 2001 to 2022 was at 158%, thus lower than in the EU (282%). Organic retail sales amounted to 233 million euros, or 1.6% of all retail sales.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

217,869 ha (5.1%)

562,395 ha (16%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

158%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

102,309 ha (4.1%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

4,632 ha (10.5%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

455,453 ha (46%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

1 †

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

654 (1.3%)

5,053 (17.5%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

18

Processors

75

971

Importers

N/D

370

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

274.1 M€ (1.7%)

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

25.1 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

33,862 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN CZECHIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on UZEI, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN CZECHIA

Source: UZEI

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Czechia CAP Strategic Plan foresees an almost 50% increase in the supported organic area, increasing to 21% of UAA with almost all certified organic land receiving support. Payment rates per ha for arable land have been increased most, also with a clear differential for conversion support, reflecting a desire to increase the proportion of arable land managed organically, as most of the current organic land is permanent grassland. Nearly 17% of environmental support, and almost 6% of total CAP expenditure is planned to be allocated to organic farming in 2023-2027.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	506 kha	750 kha (+48%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	14.4%	21.3% (+48%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	53 M€	105 M€ (+98%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	105 €	140 € (+34%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	452 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	1,235 M€	16.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,478 M€	5.7%
Total CAP Expenditure	7,955 M€	

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	84	265	536	825	900
	2023	P2	106	323	660	896	900
Change from 2019 to 2023			+26%	+22%	+23%	+9%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	83	133	466	779	845
	2023	P2	100	239	638	850	847
Change from 2019 to 2023			+20%	+79%	+37%	+9%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	100%	15%	6%	7%
	2023		6%	35%	3%	5%	6%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Czechia is now on its fourth national organic action plan since the first one in 2004. The current plan, like the previous one, has a strong focus on information initiatives for consumers and farmers, including training and research. A particular focus is the aim to increase the arable area under organic management, given the high area of grassland already converted.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET*	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2016-20	15% of UAA by 2020, of which 20% arable	3% of market by 2020
Current Action Plan	2021-27	22% of UAA by 2027, of which 30% arable	4% of market by 2027, 5% of public procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2016 - 2020)

PRODUCTION
 Increase domestic production and improve financial viability, esp. In environmentally sensitive areas

MARKETS
 Improve marketing; priority access to RDP support; improve supply chain conditions; reduce consumer prices; increase sales through public catering and gastronomy; introduce national logo; monitor use of GMOs in EU, maintain organic GMO prohibition

INFORMATION
 Increase consumption through promotion; awareness and trust building; information on environmental and other benefits; ensure organic farmers have access to information, advice comparable to non-organic; research dissemination, demonstration farms; use of RDP resources for training; include organic principles in school, college courses; increase research funding; co-ordinate research strategy; policy support evaluations; market data incl consumer attitudes

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2021 - 2027)

PRODUCTION
 Maintain support, encourage more arable, permanent crops, esp. In environmentally sensitive areas

MARKETS
 Improve processing capacity for domestic products; support for producer organisations; increase vertical integration and co-operation in supply chains; increase share of public catering; support training for catering staff; introduce national logo for domestic products

INFORMATION
 Increase consumption through promotion; increase trust and address price and accessibility concerns; support for advice, if possible free-of-charge, incl marketing, financial and conversion aspects; communicate research results in schools and higher education; technical training courses; online information portal; increase share of research funding to reflect share of land area, incl focus on animal welfare and environmental issues; improve statistical data collection

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Czechia is negligible. Czechia was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Organic aquaculture is not highlighted in the current organic action plan from 2021. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.